

Exploring interventions implemented in healthcare settings for post-fall management in older adults: a scoping review protocol.

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Abstract

Objective: The aim of this scoping review is to explore the interventions that have been implemented for post-fall management in older adults in healthcare settings (including hospitals and residential care facilities). **Introduction:** Falls are one of the leading causes of all emergency department transfers and hospitalisations in older adults. Hospital transfers from residential care are potentially avoidable and become burdensome for older adults. With falls also being the most frequently reported clinical incident in hospitals, it necessitates standardised post-fall management protocols. However, the existing research on the immediate post-fall period is limited, leading to staff being uncertain on what actions need be taken to systematically manage an older adult who has fallen. **Methods:** The Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews will be followed. Three themes: “Healthcare settings/Nursing homes/Hospitals”, “Intervention Strategies” and “Post-fall management” will guide the search strategy development for this scoping review. Sources include electronic databases such as Medline, CINAHL, PsychINFO and Scopus. Studies will be included if they describe implementation strategies used in the immediate post-fall period. Full text articles will be assessed by two independent reviewers. The data extraction tool will identify recurring themes and facilitate a narrative synthesis of the included data. **Ethics and dissemination:** This scoping review does not require ethics approval because it collects data from publicly available literature. Findings will offer insights to inform discussions with stakeholders and will be disseminated through conference presentations and an open-access publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

1. Introduction

Globally, the number and proportion of people aged 65 and over is growing faster than any other age group ⁽¹⁾. Life expectancy also continues to rise, with global projections indicating that by 2050, the number of people aged over 60 will double and the number of people aged over 80 will triple ⁽¹⁾. This serves as a public health concern, given that advanced age is one of the primary risk factors for debilitating and life-threatening conditions, leading to significant morbidity and mortality ⁽²⁾. By 2030, according to the global burden of disease in people aged over 60, a 55% increase in disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) is expected ⁽³⁾. Therefore, population ageing brings new and emerging implications for healthcare settings (referred to here as any facility that provides 24-hour clinical care to older adults), including hospitals and long-term care facilities (LTCFs). To illustrate the implications imposed, older adults account for more than 1 in 5 emergency department (ED) visits in Australia, and are more likely to be hospitalised compared to any other age group ⁽⁴⁾. This risk of hospitalisation is four times greater for older adults who are living in LTCFs, compared to their community-dwelling counterparts ⁽⁵⁾. Therefore, healthcare utilisation is greater for residents in LTCFs. This is further shown by the Royal Commission into Aged Care Quality and Safety, which indicated that 37% of LTCF residents were admitted to hospital for an unplanned reason at least once during 2018-2019 ⁽⁶⁾.

These unplanned hospitalisations are burdensome for frail residents and increase their risk of delirium, hospital-acquired infections, functional decline, and iatrogenic complications ^(7, 8). LTCF residents also face a 6-25% risk of inpatient mortality as a result of these unplanned hospitalisations ⁽⁹⁾. An unplanned hospitalisation can be defined as transfers from LTCFs to the acute care setting requiring at least one-night stay ⁽¹⁰⁾. The prevalence of unplanned hospitalisations ranges between 7- 46% ^(11, 12) however, several studies suggest that between 19-67% of these unplanned hospitalisations are deemed potentially avoidable ^(10, 13). This large variation is attributed to the term 'avoidable' being subjective and generally refers to resident events that could have been optimally managed in the LTCFs with appropriate resources such as imaging and wound care ^(14, 15). Factors such as limited geriatric expertise and self-efficacy in nursing staff, lack of multidisciplinary collaboration and inadequate support during the decision-making process may contribute to avoidable hospital transfers ^(14, 16, 17).

Falls are one of the leading causes of all ED transfers and hospitalisations in older adults living in the community and LTCFs ^(18, 19). They rank as the second leading cause of unintentional injury deaths worldwide and account for more than 38 million DALYs lost each year ⁽²⁰⁾. According to Tinetti et al. (1988), a fall is defined as an unintentional event where a person ends up on a lower level such as the ground or floor. Factors such as chronic illnesses (i.e.,

stroke, diabetes, and Parkinson's disease), impaired cognition, age-related frailty, and polypharmacy are prevalent among this ageing population ⁽²¹⁾. This provides a rationale as to why the risk of falls exponentially increases with age, with the highest fatality rates being observed in older adults over the age of 85 ⁽²²⁾. The global prevalence of falls in community-dwelling older adults is 26.5%, but is reported to be much higher in LTCFs and hospitals ⁽²³⁾. A review showed that the incidence rate of falls was 1.7 per resident per-year in LTCFs, compared to 0.65 for adults living at home ⁽²⁴⁾. To further exemplify this, a five-year longitudinal study of 25 Australian LTCFs reported that 57.9% of residents experienced at least one fall, with 24.2% of them requiring hospitalisation ⁽²⁵⁾.

Being admitted to the hospital carries its own risk of falls, with falls being among the most frequently reported clinical incidents ⁽²⁶⁾. The incidence rate of inpatient falls varies across clinical departments due to differing patient conditions and characteristics. However, the overall fall rate is 1.5 per 1000 patient-days, with the rate of fall-related injury being 0.4 per 1000 patient-days ⁽²⁷⁾. This is increased in higher-risk settings such as rehabilitation, psychiatry, neurology, and internal medicine wards ⁽²⁷⁻³⁰⁾. For example, the fall rate was reported to be 10.7 per 1000 patient-days in a geriatric department, and 8.1 per 1000 patient-days in a psychiatric department ^(30, 31). Falls for this frailer population are commonly associated with injury and carry a mortality risk of 9.6% during the first 30 days, and 33% after one year ⁽³²⁾. Other consequences potentially faced by older adults in both hospital and community settings include hip fractures (37.9%), functional decline (20.6%), functional dependency (13.7%) and depression (10.3%) ⁽³³⁾. Falls also have implications on an institutional level such as prolonging the length of hospital stay by 6.3 days and resulting in an average total cost of \$62,521 per patient ^(28, 34)

There is extensive literature on the topic of falls and fall-related injuries in older adults in a variety of healthcare settings such as LTCFs and hospitals. Studies have focused on various aspects, including risk factors (i.e. polypharmacy and cognitive decline), prevention strategies (i.e. alarms, environmental modifications, vitamin D supplementation), and the impact of falls on older individuals, such as loss of independence and fear of falling ^(26, 27, 35). This has provided a better understanding of potential strategies that can be employed to reduce recurrent falls and mitigate their adverse outcomes. However, there is limited research on the immediate post-fall period ⁽³⁶⁾. This results in post-fall management varying across institutions and being largely dependent on the discretion of individual staff.

Post-fall management, within healthcare settings, refers to the systematic approach taken to assess, address, and minimize the consequences of falls that occur in patients or residents

⁽³⁷⁾. Post-fall management involves a comprehensive set of strategies and interventions aimed at optimizing post-fall care, promoting patient safety and reducing the risk of future falls. This management approach typically includes immediate response and assessment of the fall event, identification of contributing factors, such as environmental hazards or underlying medical conditions, and development of tailored care plans for the individual ⁽³⁸⁾. Post-fall management also encompasses ongoing monitoring, rehabilitation, and education to prevent future falls and enhance the overall well-being of patients or residents. The literature emphasizes the importance of multidisciplinary collaboration, patient-centred care, and evidence-based practices in effective post-fall management to improve patient outcomes and enhance the quality of care in healthcare settings ^(39, 40).

With the greater emphasis placed on fall prevention, the existing research on post-fall management is limited. There have been a range of strategies investigated, including: exercise and medication interventions; use of assistive technologies (i.e. bed and chair alarms); optimisation of nutrition; education to staff; use of low/low beds; and prescription of assistive devices ^(24, 41, 42). Multifactorial interventions to reduce the overall rate of falls in hospitals have been published, but their impact on reducing the risk of falls remains inconclusive ⁽²⁴⁾. Therefore, as not all falls can be prevented, post-fall protocols ensure that older adults are receiving the appropriate assessment and management ⁽³⁹⁾. A study of 149 New Jersey LTCFs highlighted that there is an inconsistency with post-fall management, hindering nursing staff from gathering relevant data to determine fall aetiology and establish a plan of care ⁽⁴³⁾.

A few studies have explored different interventions to support post-fall management, such as post-fall guidance, algorithms, and team huddles seeking to establish standardised methods of assessment, communication and intervention following a fall ^(39, 40). However, the limited research and lack of understanding of post-fall management explains why there is such diversity amongst healthcare settings. Staff are uncertain about the existence and potential effectiveness of post-fall tools in reducing the risk of recurrent falls or enhancing patient outcomes. It is also currently unclear what actions should be taken to systematically manage an older adult who has fallen. One study illustrated that one in five fall-related transfers to the ED from LTCFs received a simple assessment, without necessitating any diagnostic imaging or medical treatment, which suggests that the transfer to the ED was not necessarily warranted and could have been assessed within the facility ^(10, 13). This highlights that with post-fall management protocols, LTCFs may better manage some fall-related incidents and prevent unnecessary hospital transfers and their repercussions on residents.

This scoping review investigates the interventions being implemented in healthcare settings to support post-fall management in older adults. This review will help gain insight into the type of strategies being utilised and will provide a basis to facilitate the development of a standardised toolkit available to staff ⁽¹⁵⁾. When adapted for LTCFs, it may streamline their decision-making and equip them with relevant skills to prevent unnecessary hospital transfers and hospitalisations. This has the potential to improve the quality of care provided to older adults and enhance their safety in these healthcare settings.

2. Aims and Review question

The broad aim of this review is to explore the interventions that have been implemented for post-fall management in older adults in long-term care facilities (LTCFs), hospitals and any setting that provides healthcare to adults over the age of 65 years. In these settings, the specific review questions are (i) What are the different types of interventions that have been implemented for post-fall management in older adults? (ii) How have the identified interventions been implemented in practice (i.e., variations in approach and methodology, commonalities, and differences among these interventions, at what levels are these interventions targeted), and (iii) what were the outcomes measured?

3. Keywords

Ageing; post-fall; healthcare settings; guidelines; interventions

4. Eligibility criteria

This scoping review considers literature that focuses on healthcare settings providing care to older adults (>65). This is defined as any facility that provides 24-hour clinical care to older adults, including hospitals and LTCFs, such as nursing homes or residential care. Studies involving community-dwelling older adults or those in community care, and non-clinical facilities such as retirement villages, will be excluded. This scoping review considers literature that reports interventions guiding the management in the immediate post-fall period (e.g., application of an algorithm to guide decision-making, post-fall huddles), and excludes studies that only report fall prevention interventions. All study designs were included to capture the full breadth of literature, such as experimental, quasi-experimental and qualitative studies. Studies published in English, French, Italian and German languages will be included. There were no limitations for publication dates for this search strategy.

5. Methods

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the Johanna Brigg's Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews ⁽⁴⁴⁾.

5.1 Search strategy

An initial limited search of MEDLINE was undertaken to identify articles on the topic. The text words contained in the titles and abstracts of relevant articles, and the index terms used to describe the articles were used to develop a full search strategy for Medline, CINAHL, Scopus and PsycINFO (see Appendix I). The search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, will be adapted for each included database and/or information source. The reference list of all included sources of evidence will be screened for additional studies.

5.2 Study/Source of Evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into EndNote 21 ⁽⁴⁵⁾ and duplicates removed. Other duplicates will be removed once all sources are imported into Covidence. Two independent reviewers (AP & RG) will then screen their titles and abstracts against the inclusion criteria for the review on Covidence. Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full and assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by the same two independent reviewers (AP & RG). Reasons for the exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, and if needed, reviewed with an additional member of the research team (KH) for a final decision. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram ⁽⁴⁶⁾.

5.3 Data Extraction

Data will be extracted from papers included in the scoping review by two independent reviewers (AP & RG) using a data extraction tool developed by the reviewers. The data extracted will include specific details about study characteristics; participant characteristics; healthcare setting; type of intervention; delivery method of intervention; study outcomes; and key findings relevant to the review questions. A draft extraction form is provided (see Appendix II). The draft data extraction tool will be modified and revised as necessary during the process of extracting data from each included evidence source. Modifications will be detailed in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional member of the research team (KH). If required, authors of

papers will be contacted to request missing or additional data. Consistent with the typical scoping review methodology, quality appraisal of included studies will not be performed.

5.4 Data Analysis and Presentation

A PRISMA-ScR flowchart will be used to illustrate the process of data collection and justify the number of included and excluded studies from this scoping review. Two independent reviewers (AP & RG) will then manually extract the data and upload into an Excel spreadsheet. The same two reviewers will identify the recurring themes in the included studies, focusing on the healthcare setting, type of post-fall intervention used, their implementation strategies and the effectiveness of the interventions. This will facilitate a narrative synthesis of the extracted data, which will describe how the results relate to the review's objective and questions, whilst also allowing both reviewers to determine the most common and important findings.

6. Acknowledgements

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7. Funding

Not applicable for this project

8. Ethics Declaration

Not applicable for this scoping review, which is identifying the breadth of existing literature, and not directly involving human participants or the collection of new data.

9. Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this project.

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11. Appendices

Appendix I: Search strategy

#	Query	Results from <u>17 Aug 2023</u>
1	Nursing Homes/	39,376
2	Long-Term Care/	28,500
3	Homes for the Aged/	14,781
4	Skilled Nursing Facilities/	5,276
5	Hospitals/	100,526
6	Emergency Service, Hospital/	87,418
7	Inpatients/	29,562
8	"Hospice and Palliative Care Nursing"/	2,358
9	Palliative Medicine/	528
10	Palliative Care/	63,209
11	Hospice Care/	8,033
12	Respite Care/	1,091
13	Hospitals, Rehabilitation/	130
14	Hospitals, Psychiatric/	26,068
15	"nursing home* ".ab,ti.	35,240
16	"long term care".ab,ti.	25,115
17	(home* adj2 aged).ab,ti.	929
18	"nursing facilit* ".ab,ti.	5,104
19	"residential care".ab,ti.	4,216
20	"aged care facilit* ".ab,ti.	1,466
21	"institutional elderly care".ab,ti.	10

22	unit.ab,ti.	484,553
23	units.ab,ti.	333,364
24	"ward*".ab,ti.	73,488
25	"patient*".ab,ti.	8,134,312
26	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25	8,811,040
27	Nursing Care/	31,130
28	Patient Care Planning/	39,524
29	Patient Care Management/	4,744
30	Critical Pathways/	7,822
31	Secondary Prevention/	22,665
32	"intervention*".ab,ti.	1,327,175
33	"care plan* ".ab,ti.	19,306
34	"strateg*".ab,ti.	1,520,900
35	"assessment*".ab,ti.	1,361,022
36	"guideline*".ab,ti.	474,192
37	"educat*".ab,ti.	749,992
38	"protocol*".ab,ti.	581,426
39	"program*".ab,ti.	1,079,225
40	"model*".ab,ti.	3,760,578
41	"review*".ab,ti.	2,758,512
42	"huddle*".ab,ti.	809
43	"debrief*".ab,ti.	6,115
44	"tool*".ab,ti.	985,423
45	"template*".ab,ti.	106,831

46	27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45	10,628,858
47	Accidental Falls/	28,069
48	"post fall* ".ab,ti.	163
49	"postfall* ".ab,ti.	43
50	(after adj2 (fall or falls)).ab,ti.	4,031
51	47 or 48 or 49 or 50	30,938
52	26 and 46 and 51	8,281

